

Procedure for isolation of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from plant and soil samples

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If you are interested in studying soil and plant compartments (i.e; soil, rhizosphere, root, leaves) it is recommended to sample the plant including the roots and the bulk soil.

Bulk soil: The soil particles not attached to the root, that surround the below-ground part of the plant. These samples will be called (B). Usually surrounding the root axis in a radius of no more than 10 cm.

Rhizosphere: The soil particles that can easily be detached from the root, by vigorously shaking or washing. The limits between bulk soil and rhizosphere are arbitrary. These samples will be called (Rp). Usually surrounding the root axis in a radius of no more than 2 cm

Rhizoplane: The root surface and some soil particles that are truly attached to the root and cannot be removed easily. These samples will be called (R).

Epiphytes: Bacteria living on the leaves and stem surfaces. These samples will be called (Ep)

Endophytes: Bacteria living inside the plants. These samples will be called (En)

Bulk soil:

1. Place the plant and soil in a sterilized plastic bag pre-filled with an appropriate¹ amount of 1X pH 7.2 Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS). The PBS volume should be enough to cover only the soil and roots. Be careful of not letting the above-ground parts of the plant touch the PBS.

2. Stir for 10 min at 15 rpm and room temperature. Recover the PBS. **These are the B samples**

Rhizosphere:

3. Place the same plant from step 1 in another plastic bag pre-filled with PBS 1X pH 7.2.

4. Stir for 10 min at 15 rpm and room temperature. Recover the PBS. **These are the Rp samples**

Rhizoplane:

5. Place the same plant from step 4 in another plastic bag pre-filled with PBS 1X pH 7.2.

6. Stir for 10 min at 15 rpm and at room temperature. Recover the PBS. **These are the R samples**

Recovery of epiphytes:

7. Fill a beaker with an appropriate amount of 1X pH 7.2 PBS.
8. Take the same plant from step 6, turn it upside down and submerge it in the PBS avoiding the roots to touch the PBS.
9. Put the beaker in an ultrasound bath for 10 min at low frequency (ca. 40 kHz). Recover the PBS.
These are the Ep samples

Recovery of endophytes:

- a. Prepare a solution of ethanol (EtOH) 70%
 - b. Prepare a solution of 2% sodium hypochloride (NaClO) and 1% Triton X-100
 - c. Prepare deionized sterilized water
 - d. Prepare four sterile containers (one for the ethanol washing, one for the bleach washing, one for the last water washing and one for water washing between ethanol and bleach)
 - e. Prepare sterile tweezers for manipulation of the plant
10. Take the same plant from step 9 (the following steps suppose manipulation of the plant with sterile tweezers)
 11. Immerse the whole plant (including roots, leaves and stem) in the 70% EtOH solution for 2 min
 12. Immerse the plant in sterile water to remove the exceeding EtOH 70% solution
 13. Immerse the plant in the NaClO + Triton X-100 solution and incubate for 2 min
 14. Immerse the plant in sterile water to remove the exceeding NaClO + Triton X-100 solution
 15. Wash 3 times with sterile water
 16. Take 100µl from the last washing from step 15 and plate them in duplicate LB agar plates. Incubate for 24h at 28°C;. these steps serve as validation for the the sterilization protocol.
 17. In a (sterile) blender or a (sterile) mortar add an appropriate amount of PBS 1X pH 7.2
 18. Place the plant (including roots, leaves and stem) in the PBS and disrupt plant tissues
 19. Recover the PBS. **These are the En samples**

Selection step

20. Take 1 ml of the sample (B, Rp, R, Ep, En) and seed 9 ml of LB amended with 10µg/ml ampicillin.
21. Incubate at 28°C for 18h
22. Make serial dilutions in PBS 1X pH 7.2, from the LB+AMP broth from step 21. The number of dilutions will depend on the sample type²

23. Take 100µl of the serial dilution of your interest
24. Plate them on Simmon's Citrate Agar with Inositol
25. Incubate at 28°C for 48h
26. Check the plates. Colonies should be yellow with a typical yellow halo around the colony, mucoid, with smooth borders, not spread, dome-shaped and quite prominent.
27. Streak the selected potential Kpn colonies on a new SCAI plate and repeat until colonies look pure
28. Identify with an appropriate method
29. Conserve in BHI + 25% glycerol

Figure 1. Schematic of isolation of bacteria from plant and soil samples

¹ Depending on the size of your plant, select the volume of PBS to be used. PBS should cover the most part of soil samples and the whole plant in case of epiphytes and endophytes

² Since we recognize Kpn by its yellow, dome-shaped, rubber-like, mucous colonies, if there are many different types of colonies on the plate, that won't be an easy task. In our case diluting to 10^6 proved to give the best "resolution" on the plate to be able to distinguish isolated Kpn colonies. This has to be standardized depending on the plant sample.